

INSTRUCTIONAL PRACTICES AND LEARNERS' INTEREST: IMPLICATIONS ON THE NUMERACY SKILLS OF GRADE 3 PUPILS

Anna Lee Acebedo-Rivera ¹, Revina O. Mendoza ²

¹ *Sta Fe Elementary School, Libona, Bukidnon, Philippines*

² *Lourdes College, Cagayan de Oro, Misamis Oriental, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17959992>

ABSTRACT

Teachers' instructional competence in Mathematics is essential because it enables them to employ effective and innovative strategies that foster pupils' engagement, interest, and development of numeracy skills. This study examined school principals' assessment of teachers' instructional practices, pupils' interest in learning Mathematics, and their influence on pupils' numeracy skills. Using a descriptive–correlational design, data were gathered from a sample of Grade 3 teachers and learners in selected schools within the District of Libona 2, Libona, Bukidnon, Philippines. Findings showed that teachers consistently demonstrate highly effective instructional practices, and pupils display high level of interest. Pupils generally demonstrate a developing level of numeracy skills across key areas, including number sense, basic operations, problem-solving, and patterns and algebra. Pupils' numeracy skills do not significantly differ based on the level of teachers' instructional practices. Although slight variations exist in the means across different instructional levels, these differences are minimal and statistically insignificant, indicating that instructional approaches alone do not influence numeracy outcomes. Moreover, pupils' numeracy skills significantly differ when grouped according to their interest. The results indicate that while quality instructional practices remain important, enhancing pupils' interest in mathematics is more influential factor in improving numeracy skills. Future research may explore how these variables interact with instructional practices and interest to shape learners' numeracy achievement.

Keywords: *instructional practices, interest, numeracy skills*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematical skills are essential for young learners because they build the foundation for logical thinking and problem-solving, empowering them to make sense of the world and confidently tackle real-life challenges as they grow. That is why mathematical literacy is now receiving attention worldwide, with various international studies underscoring the earlier cognitive development milestones as cornerstones for a child's intellectual and professional trajectory.

Instructional strategies involving visualization, manipulatives, questioning, group work, and even technology are interfacing strategies that aid children in acquiring numeracy skills at an early age as surmised by Clements and Sarama (2020). With a worldwide call for improvement in mathematics teaching, heterogeneity not only in the quality of teaching, but also in the application of child-centered methods continues to be more pronounced around the globe. A great number of educational systems still lean toward teacher dominated rote learning focused instructional frameworks in the teaching of mathematics in early grades. This alarming tendency only reveals the need to understand the extent to which instructional practices shape learners' numeracy skills and urges us to investigate children's perceptions and self-evaluations of their skill levels as a basis for improving teaching practices.

The Department of Education (DepEd) has developed some basic and foundational programs, including the Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy Program (ELLN), aimed at enhancing early childhood and elementary literacy and numeracy skills. Moreover, teaching strategies are often at odds with the developmentally appropriate ways young learners build mathematical concepts. The studies reinforced the need to examine how instructional approaches impact students' numeracy skills mastery while foregrounding pupils' viewpoints. Exploring these factors could illuminate how practices can be refined to strengthen the development of numeracy skills in the Philippines.

Therefore, this study aimed to examine the relationship between teachers' instructional practices, learners' interest in mathematics, and the numeracy skills of Grade 3 pupils. Specifically, it sought to determine the principal's assessment of teachers' instructional practices in terms of their use of visual representations, manipulatives, questioning skills, facilitation of pupil engagement, and integration of technology in instruction. It also aimed to explore the pupils' self-assessment of their motivation in learning mathematics.

In addition, the study measured the pupils' level of numeracy skills in the areas of number sense, addition and subtraction, problem-solving skills, and patterns and algebra. Lastly, the study investigated whether a significant association existed between the teachers' instructional practices and pupils' interest in learning mathematics and their actual numeracy performance.

This study argued that instructional strategies and learners' interest influenced their numeracy skills. The theoretical underpinning of Teachers' Instructional Practices with components like visual presentations, manipulatives, questioning skills, facilitating

engagement, and technology integration, can be anchored in Shulman's Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) theory, which emphasizes the integration of content knowledge and pedagogical strategies to enhance student learning. Collectively, these components demonstrate that high-quality instructional practices involve not only mastery of subject matter but also the thoughtful application of teaching methods to foster student learning, consistent with PCK theory.

Use of Visual Presentations. Li et al. (2024) surmised that when teachers need to select appropriate visual tools that make abstract mathematical concepts accessible, a key aspect of the TPACK framework where technology and pedagogy intersect. According to Olaghere (2020), visual representations helped learners grasp mathematical ideas more effectively, thereby supporting the development of problem-solving and reasoning skills.

Use of Manipulatives- This is a way of incorporating digital or physical manipulatives that requires teachers to blend content knowledge with pedagogical strategies, demonstrating their TPACK competence (Li et. al. 2024). As for Olaghere (2020), the use of manipulatives such as blocks, counters, and cubes allowed students to explore mathematical ideas concretely. He emphasized that manipulation through physical models aided abstract thinking and helped students internalize concepts, making mathematics more accessible.

Questioning Skills as to Li et al. (2024), this pertains to high-quality questioning and strategies to engage learners rely on teachers' understanding of both student thinking and pedagogical methods, reflecting the PCK core within TPACK. Olaghere (2020) posited that encouraging learners to articulate their thinking through questioning prompted the development of logical reasoning and justification skills. He further mentioned that posing strategic questions fostered analytical thinking and supported the formation of sound mathematical arguments.

In the same vein, Maamin, et. al (2021) found out that affective engagement expressed as interest was found to be the largest predictor of mathematics achievement among secondary learners. Moreover, facilitating pupils' engagement require pupils to participate in collaborative tasks, according to Lingnau & Hoppe (2023). They further noted that group discussions during activities allow students to explain different solutions, enhance peer learning, and deepen understanding through social interaction.

Research Questions

1. What is the school principal's assessment of the teachers' instructional practices in terms of:
 - 1.1 Use of Visual Representations;
 - 1.2 Use of Manipulatives;
 - 1.3 Questioning Skills;
 - 1.4 Facilitating Pupils' Engagement; and
 - 1.5 Technology Integration in Instruction?
2. What is the participants' level of interest in Math?

3. What is the participants' level of numeracy skills in terms of:
 - 3.1. Number Sense;
 - 3.2. Addition and Subtraction;
 - 3.3. Problem-Solving Skills; and
 - 3.4. Patterns & Algebra?
4. Do the pupils' numeracy skills do not significantly differ considering the level of teachers' instructional practices?
5. Do the pupils' numeracy skills significantly differ considering their level of interest in Math?

METHODOLOGY

The participants of the study comprised three key groups: the school principals, the Grade 3 teachers, and the Grade 3 pupils. Ten (10) principals served as raters for the 15 Grade 3 teachers on their instructional practices using a structured assessment tool. The 169 Grade 3 pupils participated by completing the interest questionnaire and the numeracy assessment test. The total number of pupil participants per school was determined based on enrollment data from the 3 schools. This multi-source approach allowed for a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between teaching practices, learner interest, and actual numeracy performance among early grade learners.

The questionnaire on teachers' instructional practices was modified from Clores and Nueva España (2023) and contained five key indicators: use of visual representations, use of manipulatives, questioning skills, facilitating pupils' engagement, and technology integration in instruction. Each indicator consisted of eight items, resulting in a total of 40 items. Principals rated the teachers on these items using a five-point Likert scale, with 5 indicating "Always" and 1 indicating "Never." This instrument measured the frequency and effectiveness of instructional strategies implemented by the teachers in their classrooms.

The learners' interest questionnaire comprised twelve carefully designed items aimed at evaluating students' interest, curiosity, and personal satisfaction in learning mathematics. Pupils indicated their responses on a five-point Likert scale, with 5 representing "Very Interested" and 1 representing "Not Interested." This instrument provided a reliable means for the researcher to assess the learners' perceived level of interest in mathematics and to gain insights into their engagement with the subject.

The numeracy skills assessment test measured the actual performance of the Grade 3 pupils in four major domains: number sense, addition and subtraction, problem-solving skills, and patterns and algebra. The items were developed based on theories and the literature review to ensure alignment with early grade numeracy development. Number sense included 20 items assessing place value, number identification, ordering, rounding, and comparison of numbers. Addition and subtraction included 10 computational items and 10- word problems, evaluating the learners' ability to perform operations with three- to four-digit numbers. Problem-solving skills were embedded within the word problems and assessed the application of mathematical concepts in real-life contexts through 10

items. Patterns and algebra consisted of 10 items designed to evaluate learners' ability to identify, continue, and determine rules in numerical sequences. The test items were a combination of multiple-choice and short-answer questions, providing objective data on learners' mathematical performance. This data served as a basis for analyzing the relationship between teachers' instructional practices, learners' interest, and numeracy achievement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the mean scores, standard deviations, and interpretations of various dimensions of teachers' instructional practices. All dimensions were rated as "Very High," indicating strong instructional competence among the teachers. Specifically, the use of visual representations scored a mean of 4.73 (SD = 0.38), while the use of manipulatives received a mean of 4.69 (SD = 0.40). Questioning skills had a mean of 4.79 (SD = 0.44), demonstrating teachers' ability to effectively engage learners through questions. Facilitating pupils' engagement was rated 4.88 (SD = 0.31), reflecting active classroom participation strategies. Technology integration in instruction achieved the highest mean of 4.90 (SD = 0.14), highlighting the teachers' proficiency in incorporating digital tools. Overall, teachers' instructional practices were rated at a very high level, with an overall mean of 4.80 (SD = 0.30), suggesting consistently effective teaching approaches across all assessed dimensions.

Table 1.
Summary Table of Teachers' Instructional Practices

Dimensions of Teachers' Instructional Practices	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Use of Visual Representations	4.73	Very High	0.38
Use of Manipulatives	4.69	Very High	0.40
Questioning Skills	4.79	Very High	0.44
Facilitating Pupils' Engagement	4.88	Very High	0.31
Technology Integration in Instruction	4.90	Very High	0.14
Overall Teachers' Instructional Practices	4.80	Very High	0.30

Table 2 shows the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of the participants' interest in Mathematics. The results indicate that the majority of participants are interested in Mathematics, with 129 learners (76.33%) falling in the "Interested" category and 38 learners (22.49%) in the "Very Interested" category. Only 2 learners (1.18%) were "Sometimes Interested," while no participants were classified as "A Little Interested" or "Not Interested." The overall mean of 4.17, with a standard deviation of 0.33, reflects a high level of interest among the participants. These findings suggest that most learners demonstrate strong enthusiasm and positive attitudes toward learning Mathematics, which may play a significant role in their engagement and performance in numeracy-related tasks. These can be explained by Hidi and Renninger's (2006) Four-Phase Model of Interest Development, which posits that situational interest can evolve into individual

interest over time, enhancing learners' engagement, curiosity, and enjoyment in learning mathematics. Overall, these indicators demonstrate that learners' interest in mathematics is shaped by a combination of enjoyment, curiosity, and social recognition.

Table 2.

Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Interest in Math

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very Interested	Very High	38	22.49
3.51-4.50	Interested	High	129	76.33
2.51-3.50	Sometimes Interested	Moderate	2	1.18
1.51-2.50	A Little Interested	Low	0	0.00
1.00-1.50	Not Interested	Very Low	0	0.00
Total			169	100.0
Overall Mean Interpretation				4.17
SD				High
				0.33

Table 3 shows the summary of the participants' numeracy skills across different dimensions. The results indicate that learners are generally at a developing level in all assessed areas. Specifically, number sense had a mean of 13.95 (SD = 3.46), addition and subtraction scored 6.76 (SD = 1.87), problem-solving skills had a mean of 6.07 (SD = 2.79), and patterns and algebra scored 7.14 (SD = 2.26), all interpreted as developing. The overall mean of 13.70 (SD = 4.23) confirms that participants are generally developing in numeracy skills. These findings suggest that while learners demonstrate foundational understanding in Mathematics, there remains room for improvement in all key numeracy areas, highlighting the need for strategies that enhance their mathematical competence and problem-solving abilities. The findings suggest that pupils generally possess basic counting and computation skills but may lack deeper comprehension of numerical relationships, estimation, and place value. Bowie (2024) emphasized that number sense extends beyond mere arithmetic accuracy; it involves understanding how numbers relate, recognizing patterns, and applying flexible strategies in problem-solving. Pupils at the developing stage often rely on rote methods rather than reasoning-based approaches, which can lead to inconsistent performance. Similarly, Devlin et al. (2022) noted that focused instruction in number sense not only improves computational accuracy but also builds learners' confidence and positive attitudes toward mathematics, laying the foundation for long-term numeracy development.

Table 3.

Summary Table of the Participants' Numeracy Skills

Dimensions of Numeracy Skills	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Number Sense	13.95	Developing	3.46
Addition and Subtraction	6.76	Developing	1.87
Problem-Solving Skills	6.07	Developing	2.79
Patterns & Algebra	7.14	Developing	2.26
Overall	13.70	Developing	4.23

Table 4 presents the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) results examining differences in pupils' numeracy skills based on the level of teachers' instructional practices. Across the four numeracy dimensions—Number Sense, Addition and Subtraction, Problem-Solving Skills, and Patterns & Algebra—the computed p-values were all greater than 0.05 (Number Sense, $p = .309$; Addition & Subtraction, $p = .083$; Problem-Solving Skills, $p = .485$; Patterns & Algebra, $p = .291$). This indicates that there are no statistically significant differences in pupils' numeracy skills when grouped according to the teachers' level of instructional practices. Consequently, the null hypothesis stating that pupils' numeracy skills do not significantly differ based on teachers' instructional practice levels is not rejected. Although the mean scores show minor variations across instructional levels, these differences are not statistically meaningful. This implies that while effective teaching is important, students' prior knowledge, and access to learning resources likely contribute substantially to numeracy proficiency.

These findings align with previous study of Vacalares et al. (2024) who observed that while instructional strategies can enhance classroom engagement, consistent numeracy gains require sustained reinforcement and learner-centered assessment. Furthermore Nauzeer and Jaunky (2021) noted that instructional techniques do not always translate to measurable learning outcomes due to mediating factors like student motivation and home learning support.

Table 4.

Analysis of Variance of Pupils' Numeracy Skills Considering the Level of Teachers' Instructional Practices

Numeracy Skills	Level of Instructional Practices				F(3,194)	p	η^2
	Very High	High	Mod	Low			
Number Sense	13.64	14.38	14.45	12.83	1.21	.309	.018
Addition & Subtraction	12.88	14	14.82	13.17	2.26	.083	.034
Problem-Solving Skills	11.82	12.36	13.45	10.67	.819	.485	.013
Patterns & Algebra	14.11	14.63	15	12.17	1.25	.291	.019

Note. η^2 = effect size. Post-hoc test used is Tukey's. Effect size interpretation: 0.01 to 0.05 is small, 0.06 to 0.13 is medium, above or equal 0.14 is large.

Table 5 shows the results of the test of difference in the pupils' numeracy skills considering the level of their interest in Math. Pupils categorized under the Very High interest level ($M = 4.63$, $SD = 0.24$) demonstrated significantly higher numeracy performance compared with those under the High interest level ($M = 4.04$, $SD = 0.12$).

The obtained *t*-value of 2.24 with a corresponding *p*-value of .029 indicates that the difference between the two groups is statistically significant at the .05 level. This leads to the rejection of the second null hypothesis. Furthermore, the effect size ($d = 0.442$) reflects a small to moderate practical difference, suggesting that interest in Math contributes meaningfully to pupils' numeracy outcomes. Therefore, pupils with high interest in Math tend to perform better in numeracy compared with those who only exhibit high interest.

The findings of this study corroborate with Nahdi (2024) who found that higher interest in mathematics was positively associated with better performance on mathematical problem-solving skills. Likewise, Brumm's (2023) study showed that among primary-school students, greater interest in mathematics was related to higher accuracy in numerosity estimation, which is a foundational numeracy skill.

The significant difference in numeracy performance across levels of interest implies that interest in Mathematics is a meaningful factor influencing pupils' numeracy development. This suggests that nurturing pupils' interest is not merely an affective goal but a pedagogically strategic approach to improving numeracy outcomes. When learners are genuinely interested in Math, they are more engaged, more willing to practice, and more persistent in solving problems—behaviors that directly strengthen numeracy skills.

Table 5.

Result of the Test of Difference in the Pupils' Numeracy Skills Considering the Level of their Interest in Math

Interest Level	M	SD	t	P	Cohen's d
Very High	4.63	0.24	2.24*	.029	.442
High	4.04	0.12			

*Significant at 0.05 two-tailed alpha level. *M* = mean, *SD* = standard deviation, *t* = *t* statistic, *p* = probability value, Cohen's *d* = effect size

Conclusions

Teachers consistently demonstrate highly effective instructional practices across multiple dimensions. They strategically employ visual representations, manipulatives, questioning techniques, and technology integration, while also fostering active engagement in the classroom. These practices reflect a deliberate effort to create interactive, inclusive, and stimulating learning environments that cater to diverse student needs. Overall, the high levels of instructional effectiveness suggest that teachers are aligned with contemporary pedagogical standards and are committed to promoting deep understanding and meaningful learning experiences for their pupils. The study found that pupils' numeracy skills did not significantly differ based on teachers' instructional practice levels. This suggests that while teachers may demonstrate strong pedagogical content knowledge through strategies such as visual presentations, manipulatives, questioning, engagement, and technology integration, these practices alone do not guarantee higher

student achievement. Consistent with Shulman's PCK theory, effective teaching also depends on contextual factors, student readiness, and the quality of instructional implementation. Furthermore, the study reveals that pupils exhibit strong interest in learning Mathematics, driven by their intrinsic curiosity to understand mathematical concepts and their desire to succeed academically, reinforced by positive feedback and encouragement from teachers and peers. This indicates that students are generally willing and eager to participate in learning activities, which enhances their engagement and persistence in problem-solving tasks. Such a motivational profile underscores the importance of a supportive and responsive classroom environment that nurtures both self-directed learning and achievement-oriented behavior. Consistent with Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000), supporting students' autonomy, competence, and relatedness enhances their motivation, which in turn promotes engagement and improved numeracy outcomes. Despite the high quality of instructional practices and the presence of strong learner interest, pupils' numeracy skills remain largely in the developing range. While learners demonstrate foundational understanding in number sense, arithmetic operations, and algebraic reasoning, they still encounter challenges in problem-solving, fluency, and higher-order mathematical thinking. This highlights the need for sustained, targeted interventions and instructional scaffolding that bridge conceptual understanding with practical application. Overall, the results suggest that effective teaching and motivated learners are necessary but not solely sufficient for achieving full numeracy proficiency, emphasizing the continued role of structured support and active learning strategies.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that teachers strengthen their classroom management skills, enhance emotional support practices, continually update their instructional approaches in line with curriculum demands, and build positive relationships that foster student engagement and success. School administrators are encouraged to provide sustained professional development opportunities, establish supportive policies for addressing student well-being, allocate adequate resources for innovative teaching, and consistently monitor classroom practices to ensure teachers receive the support necessary for effective instruction. Future researchers may further examine the factors that influence teachers' classroom management and emotional support, investigate the role of teacher-student relationships in shaping engagement and academic performance, assess the impact of professional development on teaching competencies, and explore how emotional support and classroom management intersect to influence student outcomes across varied educational settings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study carefully followed ethical guidelines to protect the rights, safety, and well-being of all participants. Because the participants are minors, parental or guardian consent was obtained, and students themselves were asked for assent to respect their choice. Participation was completely voluntary, allowing pupils to opt out or stop at any time without affecting their school standing. To protect privacy, all responses were given

unique codes, and all data were stored securely. The study posed no physical risks, and activities—including questionnaires and simple numeracy tasks—were designed to be safe, age-appropriate, and non-stressful. Participants could skip any question they felt uncomfortable answering. The researcher disclosed any potential conflicts of interest, confirming that there were no personal or financial stakes influencing the study. Results were shared with families, participants, and relevant school personnel in a way that preserved confidentiality, demonstrating fairness, transparency, and respect for everyone involved.

Acknowledgments

This study could not have been completed without the guidance and blessings of God, whose wisdom, strength, and grace sustained the researcher throughout this journey. His protection and support enabled her to balance academic and personal responsibilities with perseverance and faith.

The researcher is deeply grateful to her parent, Leoncita G. Acebedo, for her unwavering love, guidance, and encouragement. Special thanks are also extended to her husband, Jeffrey H. Rivera, whose constant support and understanding provided strength and motivation throughout this journey. The researcher is equally thankful for her four siblings, whose care and encouragement contributed to her perseverance.

Sincere appreciation is extended to Dr. Revina O. Mendoza, the researcher's adviser and mentor, for her patient guidance, insightful feedback, and continuous encouragement. Her mentorship laid the foundation for this research and inspired the researcher to remain focused, resilient, and committed to excellence.

To Dr. Mendoza, the researcher expresses profound gratitude for her dedication, wisdom, and support, which made this academic journey meaningful, inspiring, and fulfilling.

REFERENCES

- Bowie, L. H., & Graven, M. H. (2024). Using games to develop number sense in early grade maths clubs. *South African Journal of Childhood Education*, 14(1), a1493. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajce.v14i1.1493>
- Brumm, L., & Rathgeb-Schnierer, E. (2023). The relationship between accuracy in numerosity estimation, math achievement, and math interest in primary school students. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1146458>
- Clements, D. H., & Sarama, J. (2020). *Learning and teaching early math: The learning trajectories approach* (3rd ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429448318>
- Clores, L. J., & Nueva España, R. C. (2023). Assessment of teachers' instructional practices: Towards proposing an innovative instructional model for teaching-learning material in chemistry. *Journal of Practical Studies in Education*, 4(4), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.46809/jpse.v4i4.69>
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The “what” and “why” of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227–268. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327965PLI1104_01

- Devlin, B. L., Jordan, N. C., & Klein, A. (2022). Predicting mathematics achievement from subdomains of early number competence: Differences by grade and achievement level. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 217, 105354. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2021.105354>
- Hidi, S., & Renninger, K. A. (2006). The four-phase model of interest development. *Educational Psychologist*, 41(2), 111–127. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15326985ep4102_4
- Li, M., Vale, C., Tan, H., & Blannin, J. (2024). A systematic review of TPACK research in primary mathematics education. *Mathematics Education Research Journal*, 37, 281–311. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13394-024-00491-3>
- Lingnau, A., & Hoppe, U. (2023). Modelling and supporting learning activities in a computer-integrated classroom. *Computer Support for Collaborative Learning*, 683-684. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315045467-174>
- Maamin, M., Maat, S. M., & Iksan, Z. H. (2022). The influence of student engagement on mathematical achievement among secondary school students. *Mathematics*, 10(1), 41. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math10010041>
- Nahdi, D. S., Cahyaningsih, U., Jatisunda, M. G., & Rasyid, A. (2023). Mathematics interest and reading comprehension as correlates of elementary students' mathematics problem solving skills. *Edukasiana: Jurnal Inovasi Pendidikan*, 3(1), 115–127. <https://doi.org/10.56916/ejip.v3i1.510>
- Nauzeer, S., & Jaunky, V. C. (2021). A Meta-Analysis of the Combined Effects of Motivation, Learning and Personality Traits on Academic Performance. *Pedagogical Research*, 6(3), em0097. <https://doi.org/10.29333/pr/10963>
- Olaghere, A. (2020). Instructional opportunities while incarcerated: The use of cognitive skills on numeracy and literacy development. *Proceedings of the 2020 AERA Annual Meeting*. <https://doi.org/10.3102/1574964>
- Vacalares, A. B., Elbanbuena, C. O., & Comon, J. D. (2024). Differentiated Instructional Practices and Academic Performance in Mathematics. *European Modern Studies Journal*, 8(4), 199–233. [https://doi.org/10.59573/emsj.8\(4\).2024.11](https://doi.org/10.59573/emsj.8(4).2024.11)